

Development Strategies in India Concerning Education and Healthcare

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Abstract

The objective of India's development strategy has been to establish a socialistic pattern of society through economic growth with self-reliance, social justice and alleviation of poverty. These objectives are met through the development of economy where public and private sectors co-exist.

India has full-fledged to a worldwide agricultural thrust, after being dependent on the other countries for grain import for so several years. Life expectation and literacy rates in our country have doubled in the past few years. India has applied Development Strategy in their specific areas over the ten years which are 10. Rural Development, 9. Power, 8. Military research and development, 7. Media and Entertainment, 6. Tourism, 5. Economic Growth, 4. Infrastructure, 3. Urbanization, 2. Education and 1. Healthcare. In this study the researcher focusing Education and Healthcare which are essential to everyone like basic needs food, shelter, clothes that's why researcher very much interested in these areas.

Objectives

To Analyze the Development Strategies in India

To Evaluate the Top Ten Strategies used by India

To Focus and Discuss the strategy of Education and Healthcare

To make suggestions to improve their plan for the Development of India

Methodology

This study based on Descriptive Method and also the Researcher tries to evaluate Development Strategy in India through Conceptual Method.

Keywords: Development, Strategy, Improvement

Historical Background

India emerges from British rule as a free nation in 1947. The foremost 'project' that India embarks upon has been called economic development and transformation is a vital part of that project. When India became free, it presents at birth a set of institutions and policy structure from earlier times that also the economy was at a low level of development. The Administrative people devise a set of strategy to drive forward the growth and development of the Nation.

The strategy development adopted in India since Independence a rapid rise in national income and the level of living condition has been declared objective of our growth. The development strategy adopt during the early days of plan had three primary mechanism. These are

- To construct a strong foundation for long-standing development
- To give main concern to industrialization
- To emphasize the growth of Industrial goods sector as a substitute of consumer goods industries and
- To assign priority to Public sector.

Current Trend

India stands at No.4 in the list of world's major economy. Our country has developed to an international agricultural motivating force; let's have a look at the developments in India for the last ten years. We will be having a look at all the key areas that a country must shine. The Top 10 Development strategy followed by India which includes

- Rural Development
- Power
- Military research and development
- Media and Entertainment
- Tourism
- Economic Growth
- Infrastructure
- Urbanization
- Education
- Healthcare

Discussion

Strategy in Education

The Education system has witness a great extent of progress in the past few years. This is due to increased investment and various mushroomed institutes all over the country. The literacy rate in India was recorded as 74% in 2011 census. India is now ranked at number 3 after China and U.S.A in the field of higher education. An Education system in India has seen many significant changes. Some of these changes are beneficial. Let's have a look at the few of them: Online education in India is a valuable system that aims at delivering education to the students via the internet. Thus, online education is one kind of a revolution in the field of an education system.

The Private education market has increased to the U.S \$ 68-70 billion in 2012 as compared to \$ 40 billion in 2008. According to the records of Annual Status of Education Report (ASER), 96.5% of children between the ages 6-14 were enrolled in school in 2012. Women's literacy rate in India never went above 30% until 2001, when women's literacy rate touched 50% of women population, and it has been rising ever since.

Strategy in Healthcare

The healthcare system which is established all over the country to provide better diagnosis, treatment of diseases, illness, and etc. health care plays a significant role in any country's economy. Therefore, in India too, health care is given prominent attention.

In the Past few years have witnessed many changes in the Indian health-related issues. Let's have a look on a few: It was in 2012, when India, for the first time in his history that emerged as a polio-free nation. National Rural Health Mission was launched in April 2005 by the Government of India to provide better and superior healthcare to the people in rural as well as remote areas.

Conclusion

India's long-term growth has become more steady, stable, diversified and resilient. The Top priority in the strategy development is Education and Healthcare which is to be reformed and practically applicable to ordinary people then only its leads to balanced growth. The Researcher wants to add recommendations are

- Increasing More Government Hospitals instead of Private Hospitals
- Modern and advanced facilities in Primary Health center in Rural areas also
- Increase more Government schools, Gradually reduce Private schools
- Only one method of Education to all over India instead of CBSC, Matric, State Board.

- Uniformity of Syllabus in all the Universities and Autonomous Colleges
- Remuneration must be moderate to the teaching faculty in self-financing colleges and then only they concentrate to their job with stress-free.
- In future Government takes steps for making policy on Nationalize in the field of Education and Health Care.

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